

Structure III finds further support from its insolubility in dil. NaOH solution.

- a, R = CH₃ -
 b, R = C₆H₅ -
 c, R = C₆H₄NO₂ - (3')
 d, R = CH₂O₂C₆H₄ - (3', 4')
 e, R = CH₂O₂C₆H₄NH₂ - (3', 4', 6')

Experimental

Melting points were taken in open glass capillaries in liquid paraffin bath and are uncorrected. PMR spectra were recorded on Varian 360 60 MHz spectrometer. Purity of the compounds was checked by tlc on silica gel.

4-Amino-5-mercapto-3-methyl-s-triazole (I): It was prepared starting from thio-carbohydrazide⁵ and excess of acetic acid according to the procedure described by Saikachi and Kanaoka⁶.

3,6-Dimethyl-5,6-dihydro-s-triazolo [3,4-b] [1,3,4]thiadiazole: A slow stream of dry hydrochloric acid gas was passed through a chilled ethereal suspension (20 ml) of 4-amino-5-mercapto-3-methyl-s-triazole (1.3 g; 0.01 mole) till it was saturated. Ether was decanted off completely and the residue was suspended in absolute ethanol (40 ml). To this, fused sodium acetate (0.90 g; 0.011 mole) and freshly distilled acetaldehyde (2.2 g; 0.05 mole) were added. The contents were refluxed over a steam bath under nitrogen atmosphere. The suspension started dissolving and a new solid separated out. Refluxing was continued for 4 hr when it was cooled. The separated solid was collected under suction and washed with water. Crystallisation from ethanol gave faint cream coloured long plates, m.p. 211°, yield 1.0 g (65%).

TABLE I—METHYL-5,6-DIHYDRO-S-TRIAZOLO [3, 4-b] [1, 3, 4] THIA DIAZOLES WITH SUBSTITUTIONS IN POSITION 6.

Sl. No.	R	Time taken for the reaction (hr)	m.p. °C	Yield %
a	CH ₃	4	211	65
b	C ₆ H ₅	4	203	75
c	C ₆ H ₄ NO ₂ -(3')	8	227	60
d	CH ₂ O ₂ C ₆ H ₄ -(3', 4')	4	219	68
e	CH ₂ O ₂ C ₆ H ₄ NH ₂ -(3', 4', 6')	6	300	55

All the compounds were crystallised from ethanol. All compounds give consistent C, H and N analysis.

Similarly, other aldehydes, namely benzaldehyde, *m*-nitrobenzaldehyde, piperonal and *o*-amino piperonal were condensed with 4-amino-5-mercapto-3-methyl-*s*-triazole. The yield of these products, their m. p. and time required for the reaction are tabulated in Table 1. All the compounds were crystallised from ethanol. They also gave consistent carbon, hydrogen and nitrogen analysis.

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Synthesis and Antifungal Activity of Oxazolones

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4-(2-Chlorophenylhydrazono)-3-methyl-5-isoxazolone is the only compound in the oxazolone and isoxazolone family of compounds which has been used against fungus¹. During our work on the synthesis and activity studies of some new heterocyclic compounds, we found that 2-phenyl-4-(α -methylbenzal)-5-oxazolones are quite active against fungus. This paper describes synthesis of some oxazolones and their activity against the fungi *Alternaria solani*, *Colletotrichum capsici* and *Choanephora cucurbitarum*.

2-Phenyl-4-(α -methylbenzal)-5-oxazolones (III) have been prepared by the reaction of azlactone, prepared *in situ* by the action of acetic anhydride on hippuric acid in presence of sodium acetate, with α -methylbenzalbenzylamines. The products are obtained probably by the elimination of benzylamine from the addition products of azlactone with corresponding imines. First step in the mechanism^{2,3} is the abstraction of a proton from the active methylene function of azlactone to give an enolate which undergoes electrophilic addition with the imines to yield unstable addition product (II). Subsequent

elimination of benzylamine in presence of base affords III as shown in Chart 1.

Chart 1

The oxazolone structure assigned to these products has support from elemental analysis, IR, nmr and mass spectra. IR spectrum of III_a showed bands at 1750 and 1670 cm⁻¹ indicative of carbonyl group and C=N linkage, respectively. NMR spectrum of III_b showed three methyl protons as a singlet at 7.7 τ and nine aromatic protons as a multiplet between 2.2 to 2.8 τ. In mass spectra, molecular ion peaks constituted the base peaks. Mass and nmr spectra further indicated that acylation of OH and NH₂ groups also took place under the reaction conditions.

The products (Table 1) are found to be identical (m.m.p.) with the authentic samples of the respective oxazolones synthesized by an unambiguous route⁴.

TABLE 1—2-PHENYL-4-(α-METHYLBENZAL)-5-OXAZOLONES (III)

Compound	R	m.p.* °C	Yield %
III _a	<i>p</i> -OC ₂ H ₅	37	70
III _b	<i>p</i> -Cl	250	80
III _c	<i>p</i> -OCOCH ₃	100	75
III _d	<i>m</i> -NO ₂	70	80
III _e	<i>p</i> -CH ₃	167	80
III _f	<i>p</i> -NHCOCH ₃	143	75
III _g	<i>o,p</i> -Br ₂	138	70
III _h	<i>o,p</i> -(OCOCH ₃) ₂	153	70

*All melting points are uncorrected.
All the compounds gave satisfactory elemental analysis.

The above oxazolones (III_a-III_h) along with 2-phenyl-4-(α-methylbenzal)-5-oxazolone (III_i) and 2-phenyl-4-(α-methyl-*p*-bromobenzal)-5-oxazolone (III_j) were tested for their antifungal activity against *Alternaria solani*, *Colletotrichum capsici* and *Choanephora cucurbitarum* by poisoned food technique. For each compound three concentrations viz. 1000, 500 and 250 ppm were tried. Compounds III_b, III_d, III_f, III_g and III_h completely inhibited all the three fungi at 1000 ppm. The other five compounds were not so effective even at 1000 ppm. A detailed study of the structure activity relationship showed that the presence of Cl, NO₂ and NHCOCH₃ groups in phenyl ring of oxazolone increased the activity of unsubstituted oxazolone III_i. Another interesting feature of the study was that while the presence of one Br or OCOCH₃ in the phenyl ring had little effect on the activity, presence of two Br or two OCOCH₃ in the phenyl ring (III_g and III_h) made these oxazolones the most effective.

Experimental

Reaction of azlactone with α-methyl-*p*-chlorobenzal-benzylamine: Hippuric acid (1.8 g) and α-methyl-*p*-chlorobenzalbenzylamine (0.01 mole) were dissolved in dry benzene (50 ml). Acetic anhydride (1.2 ml) and sodium acetate (0.5 g) were added to the solution. The mixture was just heated to get a clear solution and left at room temperature for 2 days. During this period most of the product precipitated which was filtered off. The mother liquor on concentration gave more of the product. The product was recrystallized from hot benzene, m.p. 250° (yield 80%). Other oxazolones were synthesized in similar manner.

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Amoebicidal Testing of Drugs—Use of Goat Serum as a Substitute for Horse Serum for Growing *Entamoeba histolytica*

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A MOEBIASIS is one of the most prevalent diseases in tropical countries like India. Unfortunately, even today, the disease is not diagnosed adequately and critically though prolonged amoebiasis causes ulcerations, hepatic complications, liver